

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LANG****FIRST NAME: LYNNE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: PROFESSOR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US English

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author x did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author x did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Mac Sonoma 14.6.1

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The software Zotero is an essential requirement for Euclid University courses. After students download Zotero on their computers, what are the three main ways to add references?

- Add manually into Zotero, by a PMID identifier (advisable choice), or directly from the Zotero connector.¹**
- Cut and paste the reference into the assignment, manually enter the reference at the end of the assignment or enter using a Zotero connector.
- Zotero contains all necessary references (previously programmed into the Zotero System), and no additional references can be added.

¹*How to Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide)*, Steven Bradburn (YouTube, July 5, 2018), 12:41 min., https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JG7Uq_JFDzE&t=152s.

- List the title of the article or book and the published date in Zotero, use PMID, search in Zotero, and enter info found there.
2. What is a *Concept Paper* and its role in dissertation work?
- To explain various ideas considered for a dissertation and how connected the researcher is to the topics.
- To help the dissertation student understand the structure of a dissertation.
- To help professors understand the methodology used in the dissertation.
- To introduce readers to what is being researched, why it is important, and how the research will be conducted.²**
3. Describe the three considerations that experienced researchers keep in mind when constructing research.
- The topic that needs to be researched, the research question and data to support the answer about why the topic is important (and leads to credit or discredit the data), and the significance of the question and supporting data.³**
- The research question to be answered, the data to support it, and the research outcomes to be published.
- The right number of resources to back a claim, evidence that the research is valid, and finding the right publisher to share the finished work.

² James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida University Press, 2017), 2.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 7.

- The right school to support researchers, the right database for finding data to support research, and a good peer review panel.
4. What is the difference between pure and applied research?
- Pure* research uses only data from journals and is applied to live subjects only.
- Pure* research has only one researcher and *applied* research has multiple researchers working on one study.
- Pure* research addresses a conceptual problem without practical consequences and *applied* research addresses a conceptual problem that has practical consequences.⁴**
- Pure* research draws from nature, and *applied* research integrates natural and manufactured subjects into the research topics.
5. Which of the following characterizes Qualitative Research:
- Studying people in their natural setting, describing the setting, participants, and related experiences for contextual meaning.
- Examines social situations or interactions, seeking a holistic understanding of the experience.
- Data are gathered directly from participants by the researcher.
- All of the above.***⁵

⁴ Ibid., 29-30

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, 2019), 144.

6. Chronic procrastination and writer's block may be caused by mental health issues, feeling overwhelmed, or lacking the skill or ability to move ahead on a project. What are some ways to overcome the barriers to writing?
- Set a routine with small, achievable goals, chart progress, and find a writing partner or group.
 - Tell yourself you are not writing a draft, merely sketching out some ideas.
 - Write without looking at the page or computer screen and write routinely immediately after researching.
 - All of the above.***⁶
7. What are the characteristics of an *Academic Essay*?
- Scholarly nonfiction produced to include research findings or report data.
 - Seek to provide answers to hypotheses and communicate evidence-based ideas using citations and references.
 - Writing that is always published in journals.
 - Both choices one and two above.**⁷
8. Describe the two types of citation styles used for Euclid papers
- In-text (uses reference title at the end of the sentence) and bibliography style (end of the paper).

⁶ Turabian, 76.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

- Author-date style* (author and publication date at the end of the sentence) and *notes-bibliography style* (subscript in text and bibliography at the end of the paper).⁸
- Writing that is always published in journals.
- Both the first and second choices.

9. Name the factors that contribute to successful dissertation research.

- Good communication with professors, committee members, and data collectors.
- Careful planning using checklists, pacing oneself, writing, and reflection.
- Careful attention to detail every step along the way, solid data analysis, and proper formatting.
- All of the above.**⁹

10. Name and briefly explain the four main points on the *Checklist for Sending Response Papers (RPs)*.

- Filename and format of file to ensure consistent labeling of student name, degree and course code, course, and period.
- Contents (for readability), Form and Style (for course style consistency), and Common Errors (to provide examples of what to avoid in completing assignments).
- Preface to *Comprehensive Guide to Your Quantitative Dissertation*.
- Both choices one and two listed for this question.**¹⁰

⁸ Turabian, 142-143.

⁹ Sampson, 79-83.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 4th ed. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Bradburn, Steven. "How to Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide)," YouTube video July 5, 2018, 12:41, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JG7Uq_JFDzE&t=152s.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. Tallahassee, FL: Florida University Press, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.